

Immune Escape and Viral Persistence – Do Heparan Sulfate Proteoglycans Play a Role?

Letters to the Research Community – Entry 2

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Abstract

The evaluation of most pathogens' utilization of heparan sulfate has primarily focused on determining heparan sulfate's role in host cell entry. However, the mechanistic pathways allowing pathogen immune escape and viral persistence often remain mysteries. Heparan sulfates and heparan sulfate proteoglycans have known involvement in the clustering of heparan sulfate binding proteins (HSBPs) and cell to cell fusion. The formation of syncytia provides mechanistic support for immune escape and viral persistence.

Cell to cell fusion provides an opportunity for pathogens to infect additional host cells, without re-entering the extracellular space, where immune detection is more likely. Such syncytium formation also supports viral persistence.

In some viruses, cell-to-cell fusion has been demonstrated; however, HS or HSPG direct or indirect involvement has not been studied. Examples may include, but are not limited to, EBV and CMV.

In contrast to these understudied pathogens, the most extensively studied heparan sulfate (HS)/heparan sulfate proteoglycan (HSPG) involvement in viral syncytium formation centers on HSV-1. (Choudhary et al., 2011; Karasneh et al., 2011; Shukla and Spear, 2001; Tiwari et al., 2007) More recently a similar role for HS has been identified in SARS-CoV-2 infection. (Hudák et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023).

CMV studies provide additional insight into intervention timing. When a novel peptide, capable of blocking viral host cell entry was added after the adsorption or fusion phase of viral entry, no significant reduction in plaque formation was observed. (Dogra et al., 2015) Could this be because cell-to-cell fusion was not stopped and the virus no longer needed to attach to cell membrane HSPGs? Could the core protein still be enabled and “in charge” of clustering adjacent cells with membrane-attached HSBPs?

When evaluating cell fusion in HSV-1, the authors concluded that HS was not required when utilizing CHO-K1 cells which demonstrate a 2-3 fold reduction in sulfation (Bame and Esko, 1989). However, the study methodology would have left the core protein intact. (Pertel et al., 2001) Syndecan 1 core protein without HS chains was shown to enable syncytium formation in HSV-1. (Karasneh et al., 2011)

Even if we do not entertain the possibility of altered core protein function without native heparan sulfate chains, a bare heparan sulfate proteoglycan core protein appears to enable HSV-1 syncytium formation. Thus, we have identified at least two separate enabling functions of HSPGs: support of initial viral entry and facilitation of viral immune evasion with possible viral persistence.

Given that a subset of Long COVID patients demonstrate viral persistence and EBV is commonly reactivated in both Long COVID and ME/CFS, further investigation of the HSPG involvement in viral immune evasion with possible viral persistence could move us closer to understanding the related pathophysiology and potential targets for intervention.

[Perhaps there would be benefit in developing a dynamic checklist of exploration questions for each individual pathogen?]

As previously described, the heparan sulfate proteoglycan system symmetrically regulates healthy homeostasis. Disruption leads to pathophysiology. (Miller, 2025) Absence is incompatible with life. (Stickens et al., 2005)

Letters to the Research Community:

- Entry 1: Functional Symmetry with Asymmetric Binding: The Impact of IgM vs TS-HDS Autoantibodies on the Heparan Sulfate Proteoglycan System. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.16938909
- Entry 2: Immune Escape and Viral Persistence – Do Heparan Sulfate Proteoglycans Play a Role? DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17089128
- Upcoming Attraction: Entry 3: Research Design Considerations for HSPG Studies in Post-Viral Syndromes

I welcome thoughts and correspondence on these connections. For notification on release of new Letter Entries, please email your contact information to anisyhp@gmail.com.

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